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SCENARIO OF INFORMAL SECTOR IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

In this research paper we have tried to analyze the role of informal sector in employment of the Indian workforce. The informal sector was a source of livelihood to approximately 94% of the country's workforce. The informal sector is characterized by absence of official protection, recognition and trade union organization, Labor intensive Small scale operation with individual or family ownership, unauthorized use of vacant public or private land. There is a relationship between economic liberalization and informal/ unorganized sector in India. As trade liberalization or country's openness increases, the size of informal sector also increases in absolute terms, while the relative size of the informal sector decreases.

Keywords: Globalization, Informal sector, Unorganized sector, Linkages.

Introduction

Informal Sector encompasses all jobs which are not recognized as normal income sources, and on which taxes are not paid, largely ignores labor regulations, officially recognized collective bargaining processes. However, the informal sector could also be interpreted to include legal activities, such as jobs that are performed in exchange for something other than money. Though the concept of unorganized sector is slightly different from the informal sector, but here we will use both the terms interchangeably. The informal economy under any governing system is diverse and includes small-scaled, occasional members (often street vendors and garbage recyclers) as well as larger, regular enterprises. Informal economies include garment workers working from their homes, as well as informally employed personnel of formal enterprises.

Informal sector is also divided into two broad categories: traditional household based informal sector and modern informal sector (Ranis and Stewart (1999)). Traditional informal sector is a very small size, low capitalization, low labor productivity, static technology and household based production unit. Modern informal sector is larger in size, capital intensive and more dynamic in technology.

Characteristics of an Informal Sector

Informal Sector Enterprises in India: The unorganized sector in India refers to enterprises whose activities or collection of data is not regulated under legal provision and do not maintain regular accounts. These enterprises are not registered under the Factories Act of 1948. The Act requires all firms engaged in manufacturing to register if they employ 10 workers or more and use power, or if they employ 20 workers or more. Services

enterprises are not required to register under the Factories Act (unless they happen to also be engaged in manufacturing activities), and thus, most privately owned services firms are officially classified as being in the unorganized sector. Its share in the country's Net Domestic Product (NDP) was 57% in 2006. *The importance of the unorganized sector is even starker with regards to employment. In 2012, the unorganized sector was a source of livelihood to approximately 94% of the country's workforce. Although a large section of the unorganized sector works within agricultural activities, it is pertinent to note that 58million of the total employment in the non-farm sector was also unorganized.*

Figure 1: Contribution of Formal and Informal Sector in GDP

Source: J. Charmes (Delhi Group, 2006), Credit Suisse

There are 671 districts in the country, of which informal manufacturing firms are present in 578 districts and of these around 39 districts account for 50% of all economic activity. On the other hand, informal services firms are present in 556 districts. Of these, around 60 districts account for 50% of all economic activity. There are a number of reasons why informal activities are different from the formal economy – they are usually an extension of the household economy and startups that require little or no capital investment. Indian informal sector enterprises comprise of unregulated micro-enterprises, the bulk of which employ less than five workers, and all of which employ less than 50 workers. Examples of such enterprises are those that produce bidis (Indian cigarettes), small piece-rate suppliers to the textile, weaving or footwear sectors, small shopkeepers etc. The informal sector is also the largest employer of rural migrants in big cities like Mumbai, Kolkata and Delhi, and like in other countries, the sector serves as the only source of employment to those who are unable to find work in the formal economy.

Table 1: Employment by sector (%)

Industry	1983-84		1987-88		1993-94		1999-2000	
	Org	Unorg	Org	Unorg	Org	Unorg	Org	Unorg
Agriculture, forestry and fishing	0.6	99.4	0.7	99.3	0.6	99.4	0.6	99.4
Mining and quarrying	55.5	44.5	44.2	55.8	40.7	59.3	43.2	56.8
Manufacturing	19.7	80.3	17.3	82.7	16.1	83.9	14.9	85.1
Electricity, gas and water	90.7	9.3	71.3	28.7	69.7	30.3	79.0	21.0
Construction	17.7	82.3	10.1	89.9	10	90	6.5	93.5
Trade, hotels and restaurants	2.1	97.9	1.8	98.2	1.6	98.4	1.2	98.8
Transport, storage and communication	38.8	61.2	34.8	65.2	29.7	70.3	21.5	78.5
Services	40.3	59.7	36.8	63.2	31.7	68.3	34.8	65.2

Source: Sakhtivel and Joddar 2006¹⁸

Factors influencing the productivity of informal sector enterprises in India

(i) The informal sector in India is dominated by own-account manufacturing enterprises (OAMEs) employing family labor. Income growth in the organized sector creates consumer demand increase for several informal sector products. Relevant goods and services include transport, retail services, eateries, processed food, and garments and so on. Rapid growth has led to an explosion in the number of rickshaws in our smaller towns; the same is true of street vendors, road-side eateries, domestic help and so on. In most cases entry require the permission of local mafia or political bosses and hence new entrants have to part with some income.

(ii) Like consumption goods, there is also increase in the demand for informal goods and services to be used as input into formal production. Agricultural goods in general, processed food, fruits, flowers, forest products, handicrafts and a variety of ethnic and cultural items are used as inputs in formal sector. But because of the relatively low value added the effect on informal income, and particularly wage income, is not significant. Similarly, services like security, local transport, hosting and event management, cleaning and laundry, cooking etc are bought by the organized sector as inputs. But these services are mostly provided by informal enterprises that employ contract workers on very low wages.

Figure 2: Percentage employment in Formal and Informal Sector

Source : NSS 61st Round 2004-2005, Employment-Unemployment Survey. Computed.

(iii) A range of informal enterprises link more directly with the formal sector. They are small units working for profit. They produce items like auto parts, electronic goods, metal products, and engineering goods and provide services like repairs, assembly, printing, copying, and publishing etc. We come across two types of relations here. In one they supply the products which are then processed by the formal sector. In the other, they produce as sub-contractors for formal sector firms. In all cases, the transmission of income is hampered by the abysmally low wages prevailing in the informal sector, which results from low labor productivity.

Barriers for Growth of Informal Sector:

- a. **Location/ Closeness to market:** In the case of India, Coad and Tamvada (2012) maintain that rural firms are susceptible to problems concerning raw materials, power shortages, equipment and management. Enterprises which are located in the urban areas might face fewer barriers.
- b. **Age:** There exists considerable evidence on the role of age on the growth performance of firms. Evidence points to a negative relationship between age and growth (Variyam and Kraybill, 1992; Sleuwaegen and Goedhuys, 2002; Yasuda, 2005).

- c. **Registration:** Registration of the firm with any authority grants legitimacy to the owners in terms of obtaining bank loans, access to the legal systems which are instrumental in fostering growth (Levenson and Maloney 1998). Registration enhances the reputation of the enterprises in front of the consumers, suppliers and enables contractual relationship with third parties (Sleuwaegen and Goedhuys 2002). Registered enterprises lead to significant gains in sales per employee and value added per employee

Figure 3: Number of Firms Registered under any Act/Authority, 2000-01 – 2010-11

Suggestions and Recommendations

1. Measures necessary for bringing about improvements in the productivity of enterprises and generation of large scale employment opportunities.
2. Labor laws in the informal sector consistent with labor rights.
3. Expansion in the security system in terms of protection from sexual harassment, safety equipment and compensation for accident, no discrimination between male and female workers.
4. Minimum level of social security- life insurance, health insurance and old age security.
5. Eight hour working day
6. Provision of childcare and basic amenities at the workplace.

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